

BANKING SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation:

Banks provide financing for all areas of entrepreneurship, production and non-production spheres, management spheres and fill the budget with necessary funds. Without a developed network of banks operating on a commercial basis, the desire to create a real and effective market mechanism remains only a pious wish.

Key words: banking sector, two-tier banking system, efficient market mechanism.

The last decade has become a kind of "era of change" for Uzbekistan. The country is implementing full-scale reforms aimed at forming a market-based multi-structure economy. The creation of a strong and steadily developing banking sector plays an important role here. The period of independence has become a period of transition for the country's banking sector from a mono-bank system to the creation of a new, modern banking sector that meets the requirements of a market economy, and the formation of a system of universal banks.

The Central Bank acts as the central link not only of the banking system, but also of the payment system, organizing its work and performing the control function. The Central Bank is the guarantor of the continuous and effective functioning of the national payment system. In the modern economy, where lending plays a significant role, banks, issuing loans, inevitably bear losses associated with them. In order to avoid non-repayment of funds by the borrower, banks use various methods and strategies to reduce the likelihood of credit risks. According to the "Rules for maintaining cash transactions in the national economy" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, all enterprises, organizations and institutions, regardless of their organizational and legal form, must keep their funds in bank institutions, make settlements on their obligations to other enterprises in a non-cash manner through bank institutions. As a result, at present, the need for banking services is certainly growing.

The activities of banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan are based on the Law "On banks and banking activities". A bank is a legal entity that is a commercial organization and carries out a set of the following types of activities defined as banking activities:

accepting deposits from legal entities and individuals and using the accepted funds for lending or investing at one's own risk;
making payments.

Banks are financial institutions that accumulate temporarily free funds and provide them for a certain fee (interest) in the form of loans (credits) for temporary use to business entities on the principles of repayment, urgency and security.

In order to improve the quality of customer service, the bank needs to develop alternative sales channels, as well as conduct ongoing work aimed at expanding the range of services in self-service machines and ATMs. The development of goods and services in the conditions of the modern market is significantly influenced by the effective performance of their production functions by employees. Over the years of independence, Uzbekistan has been carrying out targeted and gradual reforms aimed at:

Increasing the stability and liquidity of the banking system;

Attracting additional investments into banking capital;

Further development of banking activities in accordance with international standards;

Expanding opportunities for business entities, etc.

The peculiarities of the organization and accounting of operations on lending to legal entities are the most interesting topic for analysis, since in this case banks strive to establish long-term partnerships with each client, predict the development of client needs, the emergence of new areas of banking business, and conduct regular marketing research. The processes taking place in the corporate lending market are exclusive. While in the consumer credit market these conditions are usually public and standard, in the corporate loan market, with the unconditional presence of internal banking standards, the main parameters and schemes for providing loans vary and are discussed. As a result of these measures, a two-tier banking system was created. It should also be noted that every year the number of individuals and legal entities using bank loans increases, and, consequently, healthy competition between banks develops.

Here, it is certainly important to note that, in order to ensure the openness of the banking system for clients and the general public, to continue work on creating modern information systems in banks, the development and implementation of a new accounting system was started. In less than 3 years, specialists of the Central Bank, in close cooperation with experts from the most

famous consulting companies in the world, developed and introduced into practice new charts of accounts and an accounting system for banks that comply with international financial reporting standards. The economic significance of introducing such forms of reporting into practice, ensuring the openness of information on banking activities, is great. Banks, attracting free funds from clients and depositors, lend to enterprises and entrepreneurs or invest them in the financial market. As a result, banks bear high social obligations. In addition, the transfer of accounting to international standards allows the use of modern banking technologies and maximum automation of banking operations.

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